

KFT Recommendation 10

Required qualifications for performing diving work within the scope of the DGUV

Developed by the German Scientific Diving Commission (Berufsverband e.V.) in cooperation with the German Social Accident Insurance Institution for the construction industry – Prevention

As of March 2026

Scope of Application

Professional competence and occupational safety play a major role in the professional performance of activities in the occupational environment in Germany. For activities carried out underwater with the aid of diving equipment, there are several government and trade association regulations that specify the qualifications required for performing underwater work in the areas of commercial diving, auxiliary services, science and scientific monitoring. Each of these areas has its own regulations that specify the respective areas of application with the relevant technical expertise and specific diving skills. The regulations each contain a training plan that defines the specific skills and how they are to be taught.

This recommendation for action provides a technical assessment, agreed with the responsible bodies of the DGUV, for the respective areas of application and underwater activities of the three occupational groups "Commercial diving" (colloquially often referred to as professional diving/commercial diving), "divers in rescue companies" (colloquially often referred to as rescue/salvage divers) and "scientific divers".

Introduction

Scientific divers, commercial divers and divers in emergency services make a highly skilled and indispensable contribution in their respective fields of underwater activity. All three groups work under demanding conditions in the underwater environment and assume a high degree of responsibility for safety, technology and operational planning. While the prerequisite for commercial diving work is usually a completed vocational training in a trade or technical field, scientific and environmental monitoring underwater requires scientifically based training in order to be able to deal with complex issues methodically, efficiently and safely. Divers in emergency services, on the other hand, require an operational and

rescue-oriented qualification that prepares them for time-critical emergency situations, rescue and recovery operations, and working under difficult visibility, current and stress conditions.

Scientific divers specialise in diving operations with scientific objectives. Their job profile is geared towards gaining knowledge, documenting natural and cultural underwater environments, and carrying out measurements, observations and sampling. In doing so, they combine diving expertise with scientific methodology and contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge in areas such as environmental research, nature conservation, archaeology and engineering. Their work requires a high degree of care, documentation skills and professional classification of the data obtained.

Commercial divers, on the other hand, are specialists in technical and manual work underwater. They take on demanding tasks such as construction, assembly, maintenance and salvage work, often under difficult conditions and with complex technical equipment. Their work is characterised by high physical resilience, manual dexterity, technical precision and a strictly regulated operational organisation. They thus make a significant contribution to the functionality of infrastructure, facilities and structures in and around water.

Divers in rescue services are specialists in underwater rescue, salvage and disaster relief operations. They perform demanding tasks such as rescuing people and animals, salvaging vehicles, wrecks or other objects, and providing support in flood or accident situations. Their work requires high physical resilience, quick decision-making skills, team coordination and the safe handling of special equipment. They often work in difficult visibility and current conditions or in flooded areas, thus making a decisive contribution to human safety and the management of emergency situations.

The three job profiles differ clearly in terms of objectives, skills, tasks and legal framework, but complement each other in their importance. This clear distinction is not intended to evaluate, but to ensure that each activity is carried out by specialists with the appropriate qualifications, safety standards and organisational requirements in order to guarantee scientific integrity, technical efficiency and the protection of human life and the environment.

All three groups require specific expertise for their respective underwater activities, as well as special equipment in some cases, which may vary depending on the activity. Table 1 provides an overview of the qualifications required by the DGUV for underwater work involving different tasks.

Table 1: Required qualifications for different areas of responsibility in insured underwater activities.

	Professional diving		
	Scientific diving	Diving in rescue services (THW, DLRG, etc.)	Commercial diving
Tasks	Environmental monitoring, biological sampling, scientific and archaeological investigations, inspections with a scientific background.	Salvage, rescue, disaster control	Tunnel construction, harbour construction, lock construction, etc. with typical underwater construction activities such as cementing, welding, etc.
Earmarking	Research, teaching, monitoring, contract research, environmental reports	Aid and rescue organisations	Construction, maintenance, assembly
Responsible department of the DGUV	BG Bau – Specialist department for diving work	Fire brigades, emergency services, fire protection	BG Bau – Specialist Department for Diving Work
DGUV regulations	DGUV Rule 101-023 "Scientific diving"	DGUV Rule 105-002 "Diving with light diving equipment in emergency services" (excluding fire brigades, THW and police)	DGUV Regulation 40 "Diving work"
Examples of professional fields of activity	Research institutions, universities, authorities, environmental agencies, environmental experts	DLRG, water rescue service, ASB	Craft businesses that offer technical work underwater.

Comparison of job profiles and skills in scientific diving, commercial diving and diving operations in the context of emergency services

Scientific Diving

Scientific diving is used for the systematic collection of scientific data in aquatic habitats. Typical areas of application are shallow coastal waters of the North Sea and Baltic Sea, inland waters, flowing waters, limnic waters and underwater archaeological sites. The aim is to collect specific data, take samples and document findings that would not be possible without direct access by divers.

Typical application scenarios include:

- Quantitative and qualitative sampling of flora, fauna and sediments
- Mapping of substrates and aquatic habitats
- Documentation through photography and film work
- Installation, reading and maintenance of underwater sensors and measuring devices
- Conducting experimental studies underwater
- Archaeological investigations and documentation of sites

DGUV Rule 101-023 "Scientific Diving" forms the legal basis. It stipulates that scientific expertise must already be taught during training and demonstrated in examinations. This includes methods of identifying and sampling aquatic material as well as data collection, documentation and technical interpretation.

Scientific divers mainly use autonomous light diving equipment, which allows for high mobility, low water resistance and flexible application options. Dives requiring decompression are less common, but permissible.

Safety management:

- Risk assessment based on scientific tasks and maximum safety for divers
- The dive supervisor coordinates the dive, monitors the divers, ensures compliance with the operational plan and oversees the implementation of the scientific task
- Communication via signal lines or wired intercom systems
- The readiness of safety divers is mandatory
- Emergency measures include oxygen supply and standardised rescue procedures

Scientific diving requires a combination of diving skills, scientific methodology, precise sampling and documented data security. The risk of an accident at work underwater is minimised by a high level of training, continuous training and standardised procedures with clear responsibilities. In Germany, there have been no known diving accidents involving

personal injury for several decades in the context of scientific diving in accordance with DGUV Rule 101-023 "Scientific Diving" (and the corresponding predecessor regulations) due to this high level of training and implementation. The German Scientific Diving Commission (KFT) is responsible for national coordination and international exchange in the field of scientific diving in Germany. The "Examination Commission for Scientific Divers" based at BG Bau – Specialist Department for Diving Work is responsible for ensuring the level of training in accordance with DGUV occupational safety regulations.

Commercial diving work

Commercial diving work includes all professional underwater work of a technical and manual nature. Typical areas of application include offshore platforms, wind turbines, port facilities, bridge piers, pipelines, sewage treatment plants and shipyards. The aim is to carry out complex tasks underwater efficiently and safely under physically demanding conditions.

Typical activities include:

- Underwater construction work, e.g. cementing, concreting, welding
- Maintenance and repair work on ships, pipelines and facilities
- Salvage of materials or wrecks
- Inspection, surveying and photographic documentation of underwater structures

Training is carried out in accordance with DGUV Regulation 40 "Diving Work". The prerequisite is a completed vocational or industrial training programme and a minimum age of 21. The two-year training programme comprises theoretical and practical courses, which are taught in a practical manner under the guidance of a BG-approved master diver. After passing the examination under IHK supervision, the "Certified Diver" certificate is issued.

Equipment:

- Mostly hose-fed light diving equipment (sLTG) for work on fixed underwater structures
- Decompression dives are possible
- Use of technical aids such as diving platforms, diving baskets, buoyancy aids, hydraulic or welding equipment

Safety management:

- Risk assessment based on technical, physical and logistical criteria
- Dive operations management monitors work tasks, material handling and safety procedures
- Safety divers and, if necessary, technical monitoring systems ensure safety in emergency situations
- Standardised procedures for decompression measures and rescue

Commercial diving combines technical and craftsmanship expertise, physical resilience and strict safety standards to carry out underwater work efficiently and with low risk.

Diving in emergency services

Diving in emergency services includes rescue, recovery and disaster relief operations by organisations such as the “German Life Saving Association (DLRG)”, “Water Rescue Service”, “Workers’ Samaritan Federation (ASB)”, “Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW)” and fire brigades. The aim is to carry out rescue and recovery operations quickly, safely and in a coordinated manner. Areas of operation include lakes, rivers, coastal areas, flooded infrastructure and accident sites at sea.

Typical tasks include:

- Rescuing people or animals from water
- Recovery of vehicles, objects or wrecks
- Support in disaster operations (high water, flooding)
- Securing operation sites under difficult visibility and current conditions

Training is carried out in accordance with DGUV Rule 105-002 "Diving with light diving equipment in rescue services". In addition to diving training, it also covers rescue tactics, emergency medicine, operational coordination, communication and operational logistics. Practical exercises include searching for and recovering persons or objects, working in currents, turbidity and difficult visibility conditions, and the use of diving baskets, buoyancy aids or signal buoys. No decompression dives may be carried out; the maximum operating depth is 20 m (30 m in exceptional cases).

Equipment:

- Mainly autonomous light diving equipment. Depending on the operational situation, hose-fed light diving equipment may also be used
- Rescue and recovery aids such as ropes, buoys, diving platforms

Safety management:

- Risk assessment continuously adapted to dynamic operational conditions
- Dive operations management coordinates operational teams, monitors divers via signal lines, radio or intercom systems
- Safety divers are on standby, emergency and rescue measures are standardised

Diving in rescue services requires rapid response, flexibility, team coordination and the ability to work safely under high stress. The legal basis provides liability protection and standardised procedures for operations.

Autonomous and hose-fed light diving equipment

In contrast to commercial diving, autonomous light diving equipment is the standard diving equipment used in scientific diving, with which the vast majority of scientific diving operations are carried out and trained. In commercial diving, on the other hand, divers are generally trained and tested with hose-fed light diving equipment.

Autonomous light diving equipment

Autonomous light diving equipment is particularly suitable for scientific dives to a depth of approx. 30 m, as it offers maximum freedom of movement. This is crucial for carrying out precise scientific tasks, especially in areas with currents or complex habitats, where a hose could significantly restrict mobility or compromise safety.

- Autonomous light diving equipment is used within the no-decompression limit – decompression dives are therefore not permitted.
- Unimpeded ascent is possible at any time; diving in structures or confined spaces is not intended.
- Freedom of movement is not restricted by an air hose, which significantly reduces the risk of entanglement or the effects of currents.
- Especially in tidal or shallow coastal areas, the absence of a hose minimises water resistance, reduces physical strain and extends the divers' range of action.
- The use of autonomous light diving equipment increases both safety (reducing the risk of breathlessness or entanglement) and efficiency in scientific work, as movements can be performed freely and flexibly.

Hose-fed light diving equipment

Hose-fed equipment is mainly used in commercial diving on underwater structures or for dives requiring decompression. It is ideal for work where the diver remains in a limited space and receives a continuous supply of air from the surface.

- The diver is usually lowered to the work site by means of a diving basket; retrieval is also carried out via the surface.
- The breathing hose carried by the diver can severely restrict freedom of movement in fast-flowing or complex environments, which can lead to hazards in scientific applications due to snagging or restricted mobility.
- Dives requiring decompression require controlled ascents with stops to eliminate nitrogen and are less suitable for scientific dives involving frequent changes of position or free movement.

For scientific dives with compressed air to a depth of approx. 30 m, autonomous light diving equipment is the safest and most efficient choice. It ensures maximum freedom of movement, reduces the effects of currents and the risk of snagging, and enables scientific

investigations to be carried out with precision. Hose-fed systems are only useful in scientific contexts in exceptional cases, e.g. for fixed workstations or special underwater stations; otherwise, they pose avoidable risks and significantly limit the efficiency of scientific work.

Summary

The three fields of activity differ significantly in terms of tasks, methodology, training, operational organisation and safety focus, but they share the basic principles of professional diving technology and structured safety management.

- Scientific diving: methodically precise, scientifically oriented, ecologically sound, use of autonomous light diving equipment, proof of scientific competence
- Commercial diving: technical and manual, physically demanding, efficient execution of technical work, use of hose-fed equipment, proof of technical skills
- Rescue services: rescue and disaster-oriented, rapid response, mostly autonomous light diving equipment for quick donning and high mobility underwater, proof of rescue competence

Due to the different objectives, methodology and operational organisation, it is not expedient or recommended to replace scientific diving operations with commercial commercial divers or divers from assistance companies. Although all three adhere to very similar and high safety standards, the technical skills and methodological training of commercial divers are not geared towards scientific questions, precise sampling or scientific data collection. The use of commercial divers or divers from emergency services companies in a scientific context can therefore lead to incomplete or falsified and thus unusable data, or, in the case of improper sampling, to irreversible damage to the object or habitat under investigation.

Similarly, it is not advisable or sensible to employ scientific divers in commercial diving or in emergency services companies. Although they have a high level of diving expertise and can often be deployed at lower cost, their skills are primarily geared towards precise sampling, scientific methodology and ecological conservation. Manual, technical work underwater, such as welding, maintenance or salvaging heavy loads, on the other hand, requires special skills, physical resilience and routine handling of complex technical equipment, which are part of commercial diving training. Similarly, operations in emergency services require quick decision-making, rescue tactics and the ability to work under dynamic, sometimes dangerous conditions – skills that are not taught in scientific diving. The deployment of scientific divers in these areas would therefore increase safety risks, reduce efficiency and make it more difficult to provide professional, well-coordinated assistance.

Conclusion

Scientific diving, commercial diving and diving in emergency services are highly specialised disciplines, each with specific training, equipment and safety standards. Scientific diving ensures scientifically reliable data while protecting ecosystems, commercial diving enables technical work to be carried out safely underwater, and diving in rescue services ensures rapid, coordinated rescue and recovery operations. **The KFT and the DGUV expressly advise against mixing these areas of activity**, as this can be detrimental to both the planned underwater activity itself and the safety of the diving operations.